

DETERMINATION OF RESIDUAL STRESSES IN A LAMINATED THERMOSET COMPOSITE USING THE INCREMENTAL SLITTING METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Residual stresses are those stresses present in a material in the absence of any external loading. For fibre-reinforced plastic (FRP) composites, residual stress development during processing can cause significant fabrication and in-service performance problems resulting in part distortion, matrix cracking, delamination, adverse effects on the stress-strain behaviour of the material [1-5], and reduction in fracture toughness [6], impact and environmental resistance. In this paper, measurements of residual stress in $[0^{\circ}_2/90^{\circ}_2]_{4s}$ laminates fabricated from SE84 LV carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy have been undertaken using the incremental slitting approach. The technique involves machining a slit of increasing depth in a rectangular coupon such that stresses normal to the plane of the slit are relieved. The resultant back-face deformation is used to determine the residual stresses in the coupon prior to machining. Residual stresses from incremental slitting measurements have been compared to measurements made using the layer removal technique and predictions using a semi-coupled transient-thermal and structural analysis. The incremental slitting technique has been demonstrated to be a technique suitable for measuring residual stress in thin (~0.3 mm) plies of a $[0^{\circ}_2/90^{\circ}_2]_{4s}$ laminate. Results derived using a constant stress approximation approach were in good agreement with residual stresses predicted using a semi-coupled transient-thermal and structural model and measured using the layer removal technique. Although the incremental slitting technique requires a computationally intensive data reduction methodology, once the methodology has been established it is easy to modify for different laminate configurations and is not restricted by the geometric limitations stipulated by classical laminate theory. Experimentally, accurate machining of thin plies in their entirety without over or under machining is virtually impossible to perform and is a severe limitation of the layer removal method. Incremental slitting overcomes this limitation by only requiring a narrow slit of material to be removed, which can be performed much more accurately.

1 INTRODUCTION

The extent and magnitude of manufacturing induced residual stresses in FRP composites will strongly depend, amongst other factors, on the properties of the matrix and fibres, the orientation of plies within a laminate or component and the temperature at which the material is processed. During the cure of a thermosetting composite, the material is typically subjected to elevated temperatures and pressures and these conditions result in the matrix liquefying and flowing around the fibre reinforcement, followed by gelation and finally vitrification. At the intra-ply level, as gelation initiates, load transfer between the fibres and matrix can occur and the chemical shrinkage of the resin due to crosslinking of the thermoset molecular chains is partially resisted by the fibres. On cooling from the cure temperature, vitrification occurs and the thermal shrinkage of the resin is partially opposed by the fibres in the axial direction due to the difference in coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of the

resin and fibres. The chemical and thermal shrinkage resistance of the resin by the fibres causes the fibres to be stressed along their length resulting in lower resin shrinkage parallel to the fibre direction compared with the transverse direction [7-9]. These mechanisms are responsible for the development of residual stresses at the micro-level in unidirectional material [8]. For multidirectional laminates, at the inter-ply level, macro-scale residual stresses are generated on cooling from the stress free cure temperature due to anisotropy of the thermal expansion of the plies in the longitudinal and transverse directions [7-8]. Another key mechanism by which residual stresses can develop during processing is from interactions between the tooling (e.g. mould or caul plate) and the laminate due to differences in the CTE of the tooling material (typically steel or aluminium) and composite part [8].

Due to the complex nature of residual stress measurement in anisotropic FRP composites, there has been a tendency to avoid such measurements by the use of safety factors which leads to design conservatism. There are currently no standardised residual stress measurement methods in existence for FRP composites. One of the most promising techniques identified in a review by Maxwell et al. [10], is the incremental slitting method or compliance technique. Incremental slitting has primarily seen development and use for determining residual stress in a range of metallic samples including cylinders [11], welded plates [12-13], and laser and shot-peened specimens [14]. The technique involves machining a narrow slit of increasing depth into a rectangular coupon of material so that the stresses normal to the plane of the slit are relieved. The resultant back-face deformation is used to determine the residual stresses present in the coupon prior to machining. The technique has seen limited, but successful application for the measurement of residual stress in laminated composites. Ersoy and Vardar [15] successfully used the technique to determine residual stresses in heavily blocked $[0^\circ_{10}/90^\circ_{10}]_s$ APC-2 thermoplastic laminates. The authors compared incremental slitting measurements to layer removal measurements on the same material as well as residual stress predictions using a model developed by Lawrence et al. [16]. The method is capable of determining residual stress at the ply level. It is in principle similar to the layer removal method [17-19]; however the advantage of the method is that much less material has to be removed and it is therefore simpler to perform experimentally. The disadvantage of the technique is that a model is required to convert the measured strains into stresses; a data reduction method that is considerably more complex than that required for the layer removal technique. However, as the stress derivation is not based on classical laminate theory (CLT), the method can be used on relatively thick laminates without the need to use samples with proportionately large planar dimensions.

In this paper, measurements of residual stresses in individual plies of a $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_{4s}$ laminate fabricated from SE84 LV carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy material have been undertaken using a variation of the incremental slitting approach detailed in [15]. Residual stresses derived from incremental slitting measurements have been compared to measurements made using the layer removal technique and predictions calculated using a semi-coupled transient-thermal and structural analysis.

2 INCREMENTAL SLITTING MEASUREMENTS

The incremental slitting approach detailed in this paper consists of the following stages; (i) the measurement of a set of experimentally determined strains, e^m_k associated with a known slit depth a_k ; (ii) a set of finite element (FE) models that are required to calculate the strains equivalent to the measured strains $e_{k,i}$ for the same set of slit depths a_k under a given set of loading stresses σ_i , and; (iii) a MATLAB routine to derive the ply level stresses from the measured strains and the results from the FE models.

2.1 Material details and laminate manufacture

The material used in this study was SE84 LV (Toray T700 UD HS) carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy unidirectional tape, supplied by Gurit (UK) Ltd. The nominal cured ply thickness was 0.3 mm. A 300 mm x 300 mm x ~10 mm thick $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_{4s}$ laminate was prepared by hand lay-up and autoclave processed. The material supplier's recommended cure cycle is only suitable for laminates less than 5 mm thick, and therefore an optimised cure cycle, developed at the National Physical Laboratory (NPL) [20] was used (Fig. 1). The elastic properties (mean values) for this material, which are required for

the incremental slitting modelling approach to convert measured strains to ply level residual stresses, are detailed in Table 1 and were measured at NPL.

Figure 1: Details of cure cycle for manufacture of SE84 LV $[0^{\circ}_2/90^{\circ}_2]_{4s}$ laminate.

E_{11} [GPa]	E_{22} [GPa]	E_{33} [GPa]	G_{12} [GPa]	G_{13} [GPa]	G_{23} [GPa]	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	α_{11} [$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$]	α_{22} [$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$]	α_{33} [$10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$]
124.3	8.14	7.80	4.49	3.93	2.44	0.32	0.27	0.53	0.01	43.2	45.2

Table 1: Properties for SE84 LV material.

2.2 Experimental procedure

The procedures detailed in this section were followed to generate a set of experimentally determined strains, e^m_k associated with a known slit depth a_k . Rectangular specimens, 100 mm x 30 mm x ~10 mm thick were machined from the laminate using a diamond grit coated circular saw with water as a coolant. Four specimens (X1-X4) were extracted with the longitudinal axis aligned to the 0° fibre direction (x-direction) and two specimens (Y1-Y2) were extracted with the longitudinal axis aligned to the 90° direction (y-direction) so that the residual stresses in the fibre and transverse directions for each ply could be determined. The reason for testing only two y-direction specimens was due to limited material availability. For consistency of measurements, care was taken to ensure that the top face of each specimen corresponded to the surface of the laminate that was in contact with the upper steel caul plate during cure. For all specimens, slits were machined to single-ply depths (nominally 0.3 mm thick).

The long edges of specimens were ground to ensure they were square and parallel. Optical measurements were made of the thickness of each ply using a Nikon MM-60 microscope at x5 magnification. Ply thickness measurements were made on both sides of each specimen at mid-length corresponding to the position at which the slit was to be machined. For each ply, the thickness was calculated as the mean of the two measurements.

A 2 mm uniaxial strain gauge, oriented in the specimen longitudinal direction, was bonded to the centre of the back-face of each specimen adjacent to the position of the slit. A polyurethane coating was applied to the surface of the strain gauge and lead wire connections to ensure that carbon dust produced during machining did not short the electrical connections. Strain gauges were wired into a quarter-bridge configuration via a National Instruments (NI) data logger and NPL designed logging software.

To monitor specimen temperature during slitting and compensate for fluctuations in laboratory temperature (controlled to $23 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) on measured strains, a 'K' type thermocouple was attached to the back-face of each specimen close to the strain gauge. For each specimen, a thermocouple was connected to a USB logger which recorded the temperature every 30 s with a resolution of 0.5°C . For measurement of the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of the laminate for subsequent compensation of strain data due to temperature fluctuations, a strain gauged (biaxial) specimen with a

'K' type thermocouple attached and connected to a NI data logger was heated from 20°C to 35°C in an oven. For CTE measurements, an upgrade to the measurement hardware enabled the temperature to be logged every second with a resolution of 0.01°C. The values of CTE measured in the 0° and 90° directions were $-8.3 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-7.3 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively i.e. nominally the same given the estimated accuracy of the strain measurement system of $\pm 3 \mu\epsilon$.

A 2.00 mm diameter 3-flute tungsten carbide slot drill was used to machine 2 mm wide square profile slits. Each specimen was loosely placed on edge support inserts between the jaws of a vice mounted on the bed of the milling machine (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Machine and clamp arrangement for incremental slitting tests.

Strain readings were zeroed whilst the specimen was unclamped and logging of strain and temperature was then started. One end of the specimen was aligned against a reference stop attached to the vice to ensure that the slit was machined consistently in the same position. The specimen was held under finger pressure whilst the vice jaws were torqued to 10 Nm to clamp the longitudinal edges of the specimen. The tip of the slot drill was brought into contact with the top surface of the specimen, the z-position was zeroed and the mill was programmed to machine the desired slit depth. A spindle speed of 2000 rpm and feed rate of 63 mm/minute was used. Specimens were machined dry i.e. no lubricant was used. After machining, the specimen was unclamped and the strain readings were left to stabilise for approximately 6 minutes. The specimen was then repositioned, clamped and the slit machined to an increased depth corresponding to the thickness of the first and second cut depths. The specimen was then unclamped and the strain readings left to stabilise for a further 6 minutes. This process was repeated until the slit depth had reached just over three-quarters of the specimen thickness i.e. the 25th ply had been cut through. Visual checks were made after each slitting operation to ascertain that the correct slit depth had been achieved. Strain and temperature were continuously recorded throughout the slitting process. From the strain response, a value of stabilised back-face strain was obtained for each slit depth and corrected for thermally induced strains as a result of temperature fluctuations during the test. These values constitute the set of experimentally determined strains, e_k^m associated with a known slit depth, a_k which were then used to compute residual stresses as described in Section 3.

3 CONVERSION OF MEASURED STRAINS TO RESIDUAL STRESSES

A key assumption underpinning the incremental slitting technique is that the material responds linearly throughout, so that if the unknown stress distribution within the material can be written as:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \sigma_i(z) \quad (1)$$

and the calculated strain response to a load $\sigma_i(z)$ applied to a slit depth a_k is $\varepsilon_{k,i}$, then the strain measurement at that slit depth will be:

$$\varepsilon_k^m = \sum_{i=1}^M D_i \varepsilon_{k,i} \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, K \quad (2)$$

and from this set of equations D_i can be determined provided that $K \geq M$. The value of M depends on the definition of σ_i and a common definition is to define σ_i to be a set of localised simple polynomials.

For a laminate, the most appropriate way to define the residual stress distribution within the sample is to describe the stress within each layer as a polynomial in terms of the z -position within that layer. The laminate (Fig. 3) is made up of a total of N layers and that at most, K complete layers are cut through in the slitting simulation (N.B. for the trials reported in this paper $N = 32$ and $K = 25$).

Figure 3: Schematic showing incremental slitting modelling terminology.

The i^{th} layer lies between z_{i-1} and z_i , with $z_{i-1} - z_i = h_i > 0$, i.e. z is measured from the bottom of the sample even though the layers are numbered from the top, so that $z_N = 0$ and $z_0 = H$, the total thickness of the sample. A simple way of writing the stress distribution is then:

$$\sum_{i=1}^K (\sigma_i + A_i \hat{z}_i + B_i \hat{z}_i^2) \quad (3)$$

where

$$\hat{z}_i = \begin{cases} \frac{z - z_i}{h_i} & z_i \leq z \leq z_{i-1} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

This expression assumes that the stress variation can be described by a quadratic polynomial. This approach differs slightly from that used by Ersoy and Vardar [15] as the choice of interpolating polynomials differs. The authors used Legendre polynomials, which are commonly used for polynomial approximation as they have advantageous stability properties for high-order calculations. It was considered that the choice of basis polynomials was unlikely to strongly affect the numerical stability in the calculations detailed in this work as only a quadratic approximation is used. In addition, Ersoy and Vardar's model geometry differs considerably to the model used here as the APC-2 laminates they studied consisted of three relatively thick layers and employed many more elements within each layer, making the use of Legendre polynomials more suitable.

The above expression can be implemented with increasing levels of complexity within an FE modelling approach to evaluate the strain response of the laminate to the application of stresses that are constant, linear or quadratic in z within each ply for each cut depth. The following section details the approach used for determining the constant stress distributions within each ply of a laminate.

If the residual stress within each layer of a laminate is assumed constant, then the residual stress in the i^{th} layer can be defined as σ_i . As previously stated, it is assumed that K complete layers have been cut. A set of FE models can be created to calculate the strain produced when a laminate with k cut

plies has the i^{th} ply loaded (where $i \leq k$) with a constant stress of value C . The strain due to C is defined as $e_{k,i}^C$.

When the k^{th} ply has been cut, it is assumed that the resulting back-face measured strain e_k^m is due to loading by $\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + \dots + \sigma_k$. The assumption that the model linking stress and strain is linear allows the measured strain to be written as a weighted sum of the strains calculated from the FE models:

$$\varepsilon_k^m = \frac{\sigma_1}{C} \varepsilon_{k,1}^C + \frac{\sigma_2}{C} \varepsilon_{k,2}^C + \dots + \frac{\sigma_k}{C} \varepsilon_{k,k}^C \quad (4)$$

In the experiments detailed in Section 2, a single measurement of back-face strain was made for each ply that was completely cut through and thus the above expression produces a triangular matrix of equations as in (5) for the unknown values $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_k$ which can easily be inverted.

$$\varepsilon_1^m = \frac{\sigma_1}{C} \varepsilon_{1,1}^C \quad \varepsilon_2^m = \frac{\sigma_1}{C} \varepsilon_{2,1}^C + \frac{\sigma_2}{C} \varepsilon_{2,2}^C \quad \varepsilon_k^m = \frac{\sigma_1}{C} \varepsilon_{k,1}^C + \frac{\sigma_2}{C} \varepsilon_{k,2}^C + \dots + \frac{\sigma_k}{C} \varepsilon_{k,k}^C \quad (5)$$

The constant stress approach requires an FE model for every possible combination of cut depth and loaded cut ply surface, which, for K plies, equates to a total of $K(K+1)/2$ models i.e. for $K = 25$ a total of 325 models is required.

3.1 Finite element models

Finite element models were created to run with v6.11.3 of Abaqus Standard. Eight-noded plane stress elements were used throughout, with four elements being used through each ply thickness. This choice of elements ensured that linear and quadratic variations of stress with the through-thickness coordinate could be applied if required in future work. The through-thickness stress variations were generated by calculating the required nodal loads through the equivalent work principle and applying them directly to each group of elements. The gradually increasing cut depth was simulated using the Abaqus command “*model change, remove” to delete the elements removed during the cutting process. The material properties for each ply were generated using an elastic orthotropic material with suitable coefficients calculated relative to the global coordinate system. The strain results were taken to be the normal strain in the local x-direction at a single node at the end of the area covered by the strain gauge in the experiment. A set of detailed calculations of strain from evaluation of the change in gauge-length showed that this approach was valid since the strain in the gauge-length (2 mm) was almost constant.

A routine was created in MATLAB to calculate the residual stresses from the measured strains and FE model results. The user selects a file containing the cut depths and corresponding measured strains, defines the ply thicknesses for the laminate, and supplies a spreadsheet containing the FE results.

4 LAYER REMOVAL MEASUREMENTS

For comparison with stresses measured via the incremental slitting technique, the σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} residual stresses were determined for a single specimen using the layer removal technique. As the thickness of the $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_{4s}$ laminate was ~ 10 mm, the specimen was machined to 100 mm square in order to satisfy CLT. The thicknesses of individual plies were measured optically as for the incremental slitting measurements. Four thickness measurements were made on each edge of the coupon for each ply and mean values of thickness for each ply were calculated. A 2 mm biaxial strain gauge was bonded to the centre of the back-face of the specimen and a polyurethane coating was used to prevent shorting of the strain gauge wires due to carbon dust. In their work, Ersoy and Vardar [15] reported success in cleaving layers of material from the parent laminate using a knife. This technique was not used here due to concerns over damaging the laminate and the effectiveness of being able to remove an entire ply. Instead, a CNC milling machine was used to fly-cut (1000 rpm) layers of material from the specimen. In order to hold the specimen in place during the fly-cutting operation, a vacuum plate was manufactured which included a recess to accommodate the strain gauge. Prior to machining, the specimen was placed onto the vacuum plate, the strain readings were zeroed and

logging of the strains was started. A vacuum was pulled on the back-face of the specimen until the strain readings had stabilised at which time the first ply was fly-cut. Once the first ply had been removed, the vacuum was released and the specimen was allowed to relax. After ~5 minutes the strain readings had stabilised and the vacuum was re-applied and the next layer removed. This process was repeated until the 24th complete ply had been removed. From the measured strains, ε_{xx} and ε_{yy} , the in-plane stresses, σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} , were calculated using the methodology in [15]. During the layer removal process, visual inspections indicated that occasionally there were remnants of the ply on the top surface of the specimen after machining. These regions of material were not large or very thick, but could lead to errors in the measurement of stresses. The authors are unaware of any more accurate technique for removing a ply in its entirety than the fly-cutting method.

5 PREDICTION OF RESIDUAL STRESSES

For comparison to the residual stresses measured using the incremental slitting technique, a cure model based on the work of Svanberg [21] was used to predict the residual stress distribution in the $[0_2/90_2]_{4s}$ laminate.

A thermoset resin has three distinct phases (liquid, rubbery and glassy) and undergoes two main transitions during cure. The first transition (gelation) occurs when the resin changes from a liquid to rubbery phase, and corresponds to a 40-50% degree of conversion of the resin. The second transition (vitrification) occurs as the laminate temperature passes through the glass transition (T_g) on cooling and the resin transforms from a rubbery to a glassy solid state. Vitrification is reversible and when the temperature of the laminate exceeds the T_g the epoxy transforms from a glassy to a rubbery state. The evolution of laminate properties during cure strongly depends on the cure temperature history and the curing conditions. Ideally, it would be desirable to simulate the cure process by taking into account the continuous development of material properties. However, due to the complexity and effort involved in obtaining the requisite amount of data and the need to introduce uncharacterised parameters, the model would be complicated and errors in predictions would occur. The observation of property development of the SE84 LV material during cure (in accordance with the manufacturers' recommended cure cycle) suggested that the cure process could be simulated using a three-step model. This simplified approach takes into account only major changes in the material properties corresponding to changes from the viscous-to-rubbery and rubbery-to-glassy states.

A semi-coupled transient-thermal and structural analysis was performed to calculate the development of residual stresses within the laminate during cure. A one-dimensional heat transfer application (LMAT Cure Kinetics Modeller) was used to predict the temperature and degree of cure through the thickness of the laminate. Isothermal differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) data were measured using a TA Instruments 124 analyser at temperatures of 40, 60, 80, 100, 120, 140 and 160°C. The maximum duration of the isothermal tests was 300 minutes and the data were used as input to the cure model. Thermal boundary conditions were specified in order to represent the autoclave cure conditions used for manufacturing the $[0_2/90_2]_{4s}$ laminate. The heat transfer coefficient of the laminate-to-bag and the laminate-to-steel caul plate interfaces was assumed to be 0.04 W/mm²K [22]. The temperature profile applied to the laminate was the same as that applied during the autoclave cure of the laminate (Fig. 1).

The predicted temperature and cure gradients were then superimposed on a 3D FE model of the laminate created in ANSYS in which the corresponding material properties and residual stress development were computed. The model geometry was a 100 mm x 30 mm x 10 mm rectangle representing the specimen geometry used in the incremental slitting tests. Each of the 32 plies was modelled using a single layer of three-dimensional 8-noded brick elements and one end of the model was fully constrained in the x-, y- and z-directions. The glassy (room-temperature) material properties used are detailed in Table 1 and the rubbery material properties were calculated by setting the glassy Young's modulus of the epoxy to 1% of the vitrified value and then using micromechanics to calculate the elastic properties for the lamina. Mean stress values were outputted for each ply for comparison to experimental incremental slitting measurements.

6 RESULTS

Typical back-face strain versus time responses measured for x- and y-direction, specimens are shown in Fig. 4. The back-face temperature response is also shown in Fig. 4 and it was observed that the temperature increased slightly as the slit depth increased, with the specimen temperature returning to ambient within approximately 2-3 minutes of the slit being machined. The return to ambient temperature corresponded to the period over which the back-face strain readings stabilised to a steady value. Fig. 5 shows in detail the strain response for an x-direction specimen for the 13th and 14th single-ply cuts as the specimen was clamped, machined, unclamped and allowed to relax.

Figure 4: (a) Back-face strain and temperature response for x-direction specimen; and (b) typical back-face strain response for y-direction specimen.

Figure 5: Detailed strain response for slitting of 13th and 14th plies (x-direction specimen).

A value of strain after each slit had been machined was recorded once the strain had stabilised. The ambient back-face temperature was observed to change by only 0.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ throughout the 3.5 hour test duration. The stabilised strain values were corrected for thermally induced strains using the measured value of CTE and the difference in temperature from the start of the test.

Figure 6: Back-face strain ε_{xx} and flexural compliance as a function of slit depth (z/H).

Figure 7: Back-face strain ε_{yy} and flexural compliance as a function of slit depth (z/H).

Back-face strains, ε_{xx} and ε_{yy} , and flexural compliance are plotted against normalised slit depth in Figs. 6 and 7, respectively. Flexural compliance was calculated as the inverse of flexural rigidity, which was defined as the product of the Young's modulus of the laminate and the second moment of area (I). The Young's moduli in the x- and y- directions were calculated using CLT on the assumption that once a ply had been cut then it contributed nothing to the flexural stiffness of the remaining uncut laminate. The second moment of area was calculated using the width and remaining intact thickness of laminate after each ply had been slit.

For x-direction specimens, as the first two 0° plies are slit, the measured strain becomes tensile and increases up to the point at which the second 0° ply is cut. This is due to compressive stresses in the outer 0° plies being released resulting in the back-face being put into tension. As the 3rd and 4th 90° plies are cut, the measured strain is still positive but decreases in magnitude as tensile stresses are released. This trend is repeated as the slit passes through consecutive 0° and 90° ply blocks with the magnitude of the increases and decreases in tensile strain becoming larger as the flexural compliance of the specimen increases with slit depth. The back-face strain as a function of slit depth followed the same trend for all x-direction specimens, although the strain values at each slit depth showed some variation which is thought to be due to the variation in individual ply thicknesses and the accuracy to which optical ply thickness measurements and machining could be undertaken.

For y-direction specimens, as the first two 90° plies are slit the measured back-face strain becomes compressive and increases in magnitude due to the release of tensile stresses. As the 3rd and 4th 0° plies are cut, the back-face strain remains compressive but in contrast to the response of x-direction specimens, the magnitude of the strain does not show such a significant reduction. Instead, the compressive strain tends to level off or reduces in magnitude very slightly. This trend is repeated as the slit is machined through consecutive 90° and 0° ply blocks up until the slit reaches the mid-thickness of the laminate. From this point onwards the increases and decreases in back-face strain magnitude on cutting through 90° and 0° plies, respectively become much larger. The magnitude of back-face strains generally increased with slit depth as the specimen compliance increased.

Figure 8: Flexural compliance of y-direction coupons relative to x-direction.

The difference in responses of y-direction and x-direction specimens can be explained when the relative compliance of specimens is considered. Fig. 8 shows the flexural compliance of a y-direction specimen relative to the x-direction as a function of normalised slit depth. As the first two 90° plies are slit, the compliance of the y-direction specimen decreases relative to the x-direction and then returns to parity after the subsequent two 0° plies have been cut. Accordingly, the release of residual stresses as the 0° plies are slit results in reduced deformation of the specimen, and thus smaller changes in back-face strain. This pattern repeats until the slit reaches mid-thickness at which point the relative compliance of the y-direction specimen increases significantly on slitting of 90° plies, returning to parity on slitting of the 0° plies. This not only means that the magnitude of the back-face strains for y-direction specimens are larger than for the x-direction specimens, but that the changes in strain when a ply is slit are much larger.

The mean and standard deviation of σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} residual stresses for each ply for all specimens, as computed using the constant stress approximation approach, as well as the layer removal and cure model predicted stresses, are plotted in Figs. 9 and 10.

Figure 9: σ_{xx} as a function of (z/H) for mean of individual plies for $[0_2/90_2]_{4s}$ laminate.

Figure 10: σ_{yy} as a function of (z/H) for mean of individual plies for $[0_2/90_2]_{4s}$ laminate.

For σ_{xx} results, the agreement between the incremental slitting and predicted stresses was generally good although a fair degree of scatter in the slitting results was observed, which was a consequence of the variation in the measured strain values. The accuracy of the strain measurement system was estimated to be $\pm 3 \mu\epsilon$ and as measured strains were small, typically of the order of $10 \mu\epsilon$ for slit depths down to $z/H = 0.4$, this level of scatter is to be expected. The layer removal results were generally much lower than the incremental slitting and predicted stress values. The σ_{xx} stresses measured in the first two 0° plies for both the layer removal and incremental slitting techniques showed poor agreement with the predicted values, which was considered to be due to the technique's insensitivity to very low levels of strain measured on the back-face. This would indicate a limitation in both experimental techniques for measuring fibre direction residual stresses in the surface plies of thick laminates.

For σ_{yy} stresses, the values measured using the incremental slitting technique and predicted values showed very good agreement and the level of scatter was low for the two specimens tested in the y-direction. The reduced degree of scatter in strain and stress values compared to the x-direction results is due to the reduced fluctuations observed in the back-face strain response of the y-direction specimens compared to the x-direction. Following this same reasoning, the σ_{yy} layer removal results were in better agreement with the incremental slitting and predicted results than for the σ_{xx} results.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The incremental slitting technique has successfully been demonstrated to be a technique suitable for measuring residual stress in the thin (~ 0.3 mm) plies of a $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_{4s}$ carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy laminate. The constant stress approximation results were in good agreement with residual stresses predicted using a semi-coupled transient-thermal and structural model and measured using the layer removal technique. Although the incremental slitting technique requires a more complex and computationally expensive data reduction methodology than the layer removal technique, once the methodology has been established it is easy to modify for application to different laminate configurations and it is not restricted by the geometric limitations stipulated by CLT. Experimentally, the accurate machining of thin plies in their entirety without over or under machining is virtually impossible to perform and is a severe limitation of the layer removal method. Incremental slitting overcomes this limitation by only requiring a very narrow slit of material to be removed, which can be performed much more accurately.

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